
School of Law

**The Eastern Mediterranean Conflict from an Exclusive Economic
Zones Perspective: Legal Challenges and Pathways under
International Law**

Purpose:

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Table of Contents

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Research Question.....	4
1.2 Methodology.....	4
1.3 Structure.....	5

Chapter 2: The evolution of the Conflict and International Law

2.1 Historical background and the Evolution of Conflict.....	5
2.1.1 Hydrocarbon and Claims.....	9
2.2 Geneva Conventions and UNCLOS.....	10
2.3 The Exclusive Economic Zone.....	11

CHAPTER 3: International Law and Eastern Mediterranean

3.1 Turkey and UNCLOS.....	12
3.2 UNCLOS and Islands.....	14
3.3 Delimitation of the Continental Shelf between the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, and the French Republic (UK vs. France) case.....	15
3.4 The Continental Shelf (Libyan Arab Jamahiriya/Malta) or (Libya vs. Malta).....	16

Chapter 4: Law and Principles

4.1 International Law with a regard to basic Principles.....	19
4.1.1 The Principle of Equitable Solution principle.....	20
4.1.2 Respecting Geography principle.....	21
4.1.3 The Non-Cut off effect and Proportionality principles.....	22
4.2 Libya-Turkey and Egypt-Greece Agreement.....	23

Chapter 5: Conclusion.....

25

Reference.....

29

Abstract

The Eastern Mediterranean has evolved into a geopolitical hotspot due to the discovery of hydrocarbon resources and competing maritime claims. This article examines the legal frameworks governing maritime delimitation, particularly the role of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) and customary international law, in addressing the overlapping claims between Turkey, Greece, and other regional actors. The paper argues that strict textual reliance on UNCLOS inadequately resolves disputes in complex geographical contexts and advocates for an equitable solution grounded in principles of proportionality, geography, and non-cut-off effect. Comparative analysis of key international cases, including *UK v. France* and *Libya v. Malta*, supports the claim that the Eastern Mediterranean should be treated as a 'special circumstance' under international law. The study concludes with recommendations for legal pathways to de-escalate tensions and promote equitable maritime governance.

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Research Question

The main goal of this article is to analyze the Law of the Sea and its applicability to the Eastern Mediterranean conflict. Although there is a relatively comprehensive legal framework provided by UNCLOS, there remain notable gaps and ambiguities in the resolution of maritime disputes in the region. This article investigates alternative legal approaches and interpretative principles that could be applied to the Eastern Mediterranean conflict and draws on prior international case law to assess their applicability as legal precedents.

Further, the article aims to understand and analyze the following objectives in accordance with international law:

- To investigate the Turkish approach to maritime delimitation;
- To analyze under which principles the dispute should be considered in international law;
- To explore international case law and determine how it may serve as precedent for the conflict.

This article contributes to the literature by framing the Eastern Mediterranean conflict as a legal dilemma shaped by treaty interpretation gaps, geopolitical contestation, and limitations of textual legal frameworks. It recommends a more flexible, equity-oriented approach grounded in comparative jurisprudence and principles of good faith.

1.2 Methodology

The article employs a doctrinal legal methodology (black-letter law analysis), supplemented by qualitative case study comparisons. It analyzes primary legal instruments (UNCLOS, the 1958 Geneva Conventions), international court rulings, and state practice. Deductive reasoning and

interpretive analysis are used to evaluate the compatibility of treaty provisions with the geographic realities of the Eastern Mediterranean.

1.3 Structure

This work consists of five chapters, including an introduction and conclusion chapters.

- Chapter 2: provides historical context and the evolution of the Eastern Mediterranean conflict.
- Chapter 3: examines the legal status of Turkey, UNCLOS, and the treatment of islands under international law.
- Chapter 4: presents legal principles—such as equity, proportionality, and the non-cut-off effect—and evaluates how they apply to recent maritime delimitation agreements.
- Chapter 5: offers conclusions and legal recommendations for peaceful dispute resolution.
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Chapter 2: The evolution of the Conflict and International Law

2.1 Historical background and the Evolution of Conflict

Historical rivalries of Turkey and Greece were flamed in 1974 due to the Cyprus problem. Since then, the conflict between the two states has been in deadlock. Further, the dispute between Turkey, the Republic of Cyprus, and Greece goes back to the 1970s over the delimitation of the continental shelf¹. Indeed, prior to Turkey's 1974 intervention on the Island for the protection of the rights of Turkic Cypriots,² the government of Cyprus had granted permission to multinational corporations to conduct exploration for oil.³ Laws were passed on matters such as oil exploration

¹ Eissler ER and Arasil G, "Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the Eastern Mediterranean" (2014) 159 The RUSI Journal 74-80, p.74

² Eissler ER and Arasil G, "Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the Eastern Mediterranean" (2014) 159 The RUSI Journal 74-80, p.74

³ Eissler ER and Arasil G, "Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the Eastern Mediterranean" (2014) 159 The RUSI Journal 74-80, p.74

and exploitations or drilling on the continental shelf by the Republic of Cyprus.⁴ The legislation that manages the latter is crucial because it states that the oil found in the area around Cyprus belongs to the 'Republic of Cyprus';⁵ the Republic considers particular legislation as a legal basis for its initiatives and acts.⁶ Indeed, the Republic also bases its actions and unilateral initiatives on UN Security Council Resolution 186,⁷ which is interpreted as giving the Republic the right to pass laws and to represent the entire Island, Turkic Cypriots as well.⁸

The first initiative for the exploration of oil was initiated in 1977 by the Greek-Cypriot leader, Spyros Kyprianou.⁹ Indeed, from 1993 to 2003,¹⁰ negotiations between Turkish Cypriots and the Republic continued for the resolution of the Cyprus issue.¹¹ During this time frame search for a partner for oil exploration in the area continued. The first-ever clash between Turkey and the Republic of Cyprus occurred in 2002 when the Republic considered the area located in the south of Meis Island and West of Cyprus of its own Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ); it granted permission to a Norwegian company to search for oil in the area.¹² Consequently, a Turkish frigate escorted the

⁴ Continental Shelf Law, Law No.8 of 5 April 1974

⁵ Continental Shelf Law, Law No.8 of 5 April 1974

⁶ Eissler ER and Arasıl G, "Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the Eastern Mediterranean" (2014) 159 The RUSI Journal 74-80, p.74

⁷ UNSC Res 186 (4 March 1964) UN Doc S/RES/186

⁸ Eissler ER and Arasıl G, "Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the Eastern Mediterranean" (2014) 159 The RUSI Journal 74-80, p.74

⁹ Eissler ER and Arasıl G, "Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the Eastern Mediterranean" (2014) 159 The RUSI Journal 74-80, p.74

¹⁰ Eissler ER and Arasıl G, "Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the Eastern Mediterranean" (2014) 159 The RUSI Journal 74-80, p.74

¹¹ Çakırözler U, ' "Akdeniz'De 'Yetki Alanı' Yok' ('No 'Jurisdiction' in the Mediterranean')"
Milliyet Gazetesi (February 2, 2007)

¹² Eissler ER and Arasıl G, "Maritime Boundary Delimitation in the Eastern Mediterranean" (2014) 159 The RUSI Journal 74-80, p.74

ship deployed by the company out of the area by the order that came from Ankara. The following year, in 2003, the Republic signed an agreement with Egypt on the delimitation of the exclusive economic zone.¹³ Further, in 2007, a similar agreement between Cyprus and Lebanon was concluded, shortly after the Republic passed a new law declaring thirteen oil exploration zones within the scope of the agreements it had concluded with Egypt and Lebanon.¹⁴

With the successful operation of offshore drilling rigs, political disputes have intensified, adding to the geostrategic significance of the Eastern Mediterranean. In 2009, three major offshore gas fields, Tamar, Dalit, and Leviathan, were discovered by Israel; the particular fields are expected to represent over 200 years' worth of Israel's current natural gas consumption.¹⁵ Because of the discoveries, the interests of other coastal states were sparked to explore potential oil and natural gas reserves. In 2015, Italy's state-regulated oil and gas company ENI found a vast gas field off the Egyptian coast.¹⁶ Indeed, the Zohr field is expected to become one of the largest natural gas fields in the region.¹⁷ In 2018, another discovery occurred; the Greek Administration of Southern Cyprus (GASC), also considered to be the valid government of the Island, found a gas field called Calypso.¹⁸

¹³ Çakırözer U, ' "Akdeniz'De 'Yetki Alanı' Yok' ('No 'Jurisdiction' in the Mediterranean)'" *Milliyet Gazetesi* (February 2, 2007)

¹⁴ PEKER HS, ÖZTÜRK OKTAY K and ŞENSOY Y, "Doğu akdeniz'De deniz Yetki Alanlari Ve Enerji Kaynaklari çerçevesinde türkiye'nin enerji güvenliği" (2019) 8 Güvenlik Bilimleri Dergisi 85-106, p.98

¹⁵ Erdoğan A, "The Legal and Political Aspects of the Eastern Mediterranean: What Is at Stake?" (2021) 23 *Insight Turkey* pp. 77-98, p.78

¹⁶ "Eni Discovers a Supergiant Gas Field in the Egyptian Offshore, the Largest Ever Found in the Mediterranean Sea" (30 August, 2015) (Press Release)

¹⁷ "Eni Discovers a Supergiant Gas Field in the Egyptian Offshore, the Largest Ever Found in the Mediterranean Sea" (30 August, 2015) (Press Release)

¹⁸ Erdoğan A, "The Legal and Political Aspects of the Eastern Mediterranean: What Is at Stake?" (2021) 23 *Insight Turkey* pp. 77-98, p.78

The long rivalry between Turkey, Greece, and the GASC escalated due to natural resource discoveries. The dispute not only evolved around a rivalry between these states but also based on legal and political dimensions. There are conflicting claims in the delimitation of maritime zones in the Eastern Mediterranean and legal issues regarding the Maritime boundaries of Turkey and Exclusive Economic Zones.

Firstly one of the main issues regarding maritime conflict or dispute between Greece and Turkey is Ankara is not a party to the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) of 1982, and Greece is a party.¹⁹ Furthermore, the question of the Greece Islands, the number of islands, and their closeness to Turkish coastlines is a problematic matter. According to Greece, based on UNCLOS, islands have their own continental shelves.²⁰ On the contrary, Turkey argues that UNCLOS is a treaty among states; it does not constitute International Law as a whole in a particular matter.²¹ As a matter of fact, considering the close proximity of islands to the Turkish coast, the islands may establish a coastal blockade on Turkey because of the number of Islands and their closeness.²²

Another legal aspect of the conflict is the EEZ agreements that have been signed among states in the Mediterranean. For instance, Turkey signed a delimitation agreement with Libya's UN-recognized Government of National Accord (GNA) that defines the boundaries of the continental

¹⁹ Basaran H.R, "THE LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN QUESTION" [2021] SETA 7-14, p.8

²⁰ Basaran H.R, "THE LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN QUESTION" [2021] SETA 7-14, p.8

²¹ Basaran H.R, "THE LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN QUESTION" [2021] SETA 7-14, p.8

²² Basaran H.R, "THE LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN QUESTION" [2021] SETA 7-14, p.12

shelf of the two states.²³ On the other hand, Greece and Egypt also signed a deal on the delimitation of maritime jurisdiction.²⁴ The Turkish Foreign Ministry said the agreement was ‘null and void,’ and the area marked as EEZ of Greece and Egypt overlaps with Turkish and Libyan claims.²⁵

2.1.1 Hydrocarbon and Claims

The discovery of major offshore gas fields by Israel in 2009 has sparked the interest of coastal states to conduct explorations for potential hydrocarbon reserves. With the Mediterranean becoming geostrategically critical,²⁶ the sparks of new conflict evolved because of the discoveries. Turkey joined the race for natural resource exploration by assigning the Barbaros Hayrettin Pasha²⁷, the first seismic vessel, and two drilling vessels, Fatih and Yavuz.²⁸ One of the purposes of this act was to protect the interests of Turkey and the Turkish Republic of North Cyprus (TRNC) in the region. This act was met with an objection from Greece and the Greek Administration of Southern Cyprus (GASC); it was claimed that the grounds that Turkey was conducting research fell into their

²³ Sagsen I, “Türkiye-Libya Anlaşması: Doğu Akdeniz’de Jeopolitik Denklem Değişiyor” (*Anadolu Agency*, December 2, 2019) <from <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/africa/analysis-strategic-legal-aspects-of-turkey-libya-deal/1673079>>

²⁴ Erdoğan A, “The Legal and Political Aspects of the Eastern Mediterranean: What Is at Stake?” (2021) 23 *Insight Turkey* pp. 77-98, p.79

²⁵ “Turkey Declares Egypt-Greece Maritime Deal ‘Null and Void’” (*Middle East Eye* August 6, 2020) <<https://www.middleeasteye.net/news/turkey-slams-egypt-greece-maritime-agreement-eastern-mediterranean>> accessed August 25, 2022

²⁶ Erdoğan A, “The Legal and Political Aspects of the Eastern Mediterranean: What Is at Stake?” (2021) 23 *Insight Turkey* pp. 77-98, p.78

²⁷ Temizer M and Bir B, “Turkey to Continue Exploration in E. Mediterranean” (*Anadolu Ajansı* July 16, 2019) <<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/economy/turkey-to-continue-exploration-in-e-mediterranean/1533293>>

²⁸ Temizer M and Bir B, “Turkey to Continue Exploration in E. Mediterranean” (*Anadolu Ajansı* July 16, 2019) <<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/economy/turkey-to-continue-exploration-in-e-mediterranean/1533293>>

own continental shelf and the explorations were illegal.²⁹ On the contrary, Turkish officials sent a letter to UN General Assembly indicating that the area where exploration activities are conducted falls into Turkish maritime jurisdiction and was part of the Continental Shelf that Turkey declared to the UN.³⁰ From Greece and GASC's standpoint, Ankara's actions are considered to be illegal, and it was argued that the sovereign rights of the GASC have been breached in its exclusive economic zone.

2.2 Geneva Conventions and UNCLOS

Law of the Sea regulates the status quo at sea; in fact, a considerable part of this law is codified in the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)³¹. Law of the seas does not have a particular source; it is a mixture of customary international law and treaty law, both multilateral and bilateral treaties.³² Indeed, the first UN Conference on the law of the sea was carried out in 1958 in Geneva.³³ During the Conference, four multilateral treaties covering different features of the sea were adopted. The Convention on the Territorial Sea and Contiguous Zone, other treaties that were adopted at the Conference were the Convention on Fishing and Conservation of Living Resources.³⁴ Additionally, Convention on the High Seas and

²⁹ Smith H, "Turkey Rejects Claims It Is Drilling Illegally for Gas off Cyprus" (*The Guardian* July 11, 2019) <<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/jul/11/turkey-rejects-claims-drilling-illegally-gas-off-cyprus>>

³⁰ UNGA Letter (18 March, 2019) UN Doc A/73/804

³¹ Ahmed A, "International Law of the Sea: An Overlook and Case Study" (2017) 08 Beijing Law Review 21 p.23

³² Ahmed A, "International Law of the Sea: An Overlook and Case Study" (2017) 08 Beijing Law Review 21 p.22

³³ Ahmed A, "International Law of the Sea: An Overlook and Case Study" (2017) 08 Beijing Law Review 21 p.22

³⁴ Ahmed A, "International Law of the Sea: An Overlook and Case Study" (2017) 08 Beijing Law Review 21 p.23

Convention on the Continental Shelf were adopted in 1958.³⁵ Although all these Conventions are in force, the 1982 UN Convention on the Law of the Sea has superseded them in many aspects, mainly from the general application aspect.³⁶ Nevertheless, for non-party states, such as the US, the 1982 Convention is silent; for the affairs that 1982 Convention is silent, the 1958 Conventions comes into the act to regulate inter-state relations among party states to the treaties.³⁷ However, for the states that are not a party to either the 1958 Conventions or the 1982 Convention, in this case, the applicable law is Customary International Law.³⁸ It should also be taken into account that principles composed in the 1958 and 1982 Conventions may have evolved into Customary International Law.

As indicated in the previous section, the 1958 and 1982 Conventions have contributed to the evolvement of Customary International Law. In a similar manner, during the drafting process of the treaties existing Customary laws at the time were integrated into these Conventions. Furthermore, there are still principles of Customary law that are not reflected in any treaty text or have been integrated into such text; these rules are still binding on states with all other Customary laws.

2.3 The Exclusive Economic Zone

Although origins of Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) may be found in the Exclusive Fisheries Zones (EFZ) and acknowledged by the ICJ valid in the Fisheries Jurisdiction Cases (UK vs. Iceland) 1974 ICJ Rep 3.³⁹ Indeed, the evolvement of EEZ was mainly based on the negotiations

³⁵ Ahmed A, "International Law of the Sea: An Overlook and Case Study" (2017) 08 Beijing Law Review 21 p.23

³⁶Ahmed A, "International Law of the Sea: An Overlook and Case Study" (2017) 08 Beijing Law Review 21 p.23

³⁷ Dixon, Martin. , *'Textbook on International Law'*, (Fifth edn, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005). p.196

³⁸ Dixon, Martin. , *'Textbook on International Law'*, (Fifth edn, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005). p.196

³⁹ Anglo-Norwegian Fisheries Jurisdiction Case (England vs. Norway; ICJ, 1951)

in the Third UN Conference and its adoption in the domestic legislations of several states.⁴⁰

Additionally, one of the recognized features of the 1982 Convention was its impact on Customary International Law; the treaty played a role in the development of EEZ. In the Continental Shelf Case (Tunisia vs. Libya) 1982 ICJ Rep 18, the International Court of Justice (ICJ) indicated that the notion of the EEZ has also evolved into Customary Law.⁴¹

Indeed, Exclusive Economic Zone extends up to 200 miles from the baselines of the territorial sea. According to Article 56 of UNCLOS, in this range, coastal states are provided with a right to explore and exploit both non-living and living and conduct research in this area. Exclusive Economic Zones are considered to be 'sui juris', where many rights of high seas are protected, yet the state has certain exclusive rights. The coastal state possesses all "sovereign rights" over all the natural resources over the EEZ.⁴²

CHAPTER 3: International Law and Eastern Mediterranean

3.1 Turkey and UNCLOS

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea was the result of the third UN Conference. The Convention represents both the progressive evolution of international law and the codification of customary principles. An essential part of the Convention may be considered to be a comprehensive or package deal for the states.⁴³ The treaty established a connection between

⁴⁰ Dixon, Martin. , *'Textbook on International Law'*, (Fifth edn, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005). p.202

⁴¹ Dixon, Martin. , *'Textbook on International Law'*, (Fifth edn, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005). p.204

⁴² Dixon, Martin. , *'Textbook on International Law'*, (Fifth edn, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005). p.204

⁴³ Türmen R, "Whose Sea? A Turkish International Law Perspective on the Greek-Turkish Disputes" (*Institut Montaigne* October 19, 2020) <<https://www.institutmontaigne.org/en/blog/whose-sea-turkish-international-law-perspective-greek-turkish-disputes>>

traditional law of the sea issues, such as innocent passage and freedom on high seas, and recently developing matters like seabed authority.⁴⁴ States that are party to the Convention were expected to acknowledge the whole package deal that the treaty was offering. The approval of the Convention was in unfavorable terms for Turkey because of the dispute in the Aegean Sea. The most concerning part of the treaty for Turkey was the application of the 12 nautical miles territorial sea rule in the Aegean sea.⁴⁵ The particular rule or law would transform the Aegean sea into a Greek lake due to the existing number of Greek Islands. The provision would lock Turkey out of the Aegean sea and restrict it to its territorial waters.⁴⁶ Additionally, such a deal would decrease the maritime jurisdiction areas; for instance: Turkey's economic zone to be delimited, which would also be significantly diminished. Thus, the Turkish delegation participating in the Law of the Sea Conference proposed multiple proposals for accepting the 12-mile principle⁴⁷, but they set a condition that the Aegean sea would be excluded from the Convention. The proposals were met with strong opposition from states with the Islands.⁴⁸ Indeed, in the inter-state informal meetings, states with islands argued that Turkey was trying to resolve its delimitation question by distorting the regime of islands, the islands are part of states, and they should be entitled to possess the same

⁴⁴ Türmen R, "Whose Sea? A Turkish International Law Perspective on the Greek-Turkish Disputes" (*Institut Montaigne* October 19, 2020) <<https://www.institutmontaigne.org/en/blog/whose-sea-turkish-international-law-perspective-greek-turkish-disputes>>

⁴⁵ Türmen R, "Whose Sea? A Turkish International Law Perspective on the Greek-Turkish Disputes" (*Institut Montaigne* October 19, 2020) <<https://www.institutmontaigne.org/en/blog/whose-sea-turkish-international-law-perspective-greek-turkish-disputes>>

⁴⁶ Basaran HR, "THE LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN QUESTION" [2021] SETA 7-14, p.12

⁴⁷ Türmen R, "Whose Sea? A Turkish International Law Perspective on the Greek-Turkish Disputes" (*Institut Montaigne* October 19, 2020) <<https://www.institutmontaigne.org/en/blog/whose-sea-turkish-international-law-perspective-greek-turkish-disputes>>

⁴⁸ Türmen R, "Whose Sea? A Turkish International Law Perspective on the Greek-Turkish Disputes" (*Institut Montaigne*, October 19, 2020) <<https://www.institutmontaigne.org/en/blog/whose-sea-turkish-international-law-perspective-greek-turkish-disputes>>

maritime spaces. As an outcome of these meetings and conferences, today, Turkey is one of the states which have not signed or ratified the UNCLOS. It is worth noting that Turkey's objection was not against the application of the 12 nautical miles rule but its application to the Aegean sea because of the Greek Island's proximity to the Turkish coastal line.⁴⁹

3.2 UNCLOS and Islands

One of the legal problems that Turkey and Greece are facing is the delimitation of the Continental Shelf. From Greece's standpoint, UNCLOS clearly states that islands are entitled to the rights of the continental shelf.⁵⁰ Indeed, according to Article 121 of UNCLOS, islands are naturally established areas of land which are surrounded by water.⁵¹ They may possess territorial water, exclusive economic zones, contiguous zone, and continental shelf. Based on article 121 of UNCLOS, Greece Islands have the right to claim their continental shelves.⁵² However, considering the circumstances in the Aegean sea and the Mediterranean, this act will land lock Turkey and provide Greece with a substantial advantage in the region. Further, non-party states to a treaty are not bound by the principles of the Convention; thus, Turkey is not bound by the Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS). Despite UNCLOS's comprehensive nature, it should be taken into account that UNCLOS is only one source of international law and a treaty that binds only the states party to it. Greece cannot invoke the Convention to a non-signatory determined objector. Otherwise, it would violate the principle of good faith and boil down to the abuse of international law.

⁴⁹ Türmen R, "Whose Sea? A Turkish International Law Perspective on the Greek-Turkish Disputes" (*Institut Montaigne*, October 19, 2020) <<https://www.institutmontaigne.org/en/blog/whose-sea-turkish-international-law-perspective-greek-turkish-disputes>>

⁵⁰ Basaran H.R, "THE LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN QUESTION" [2021] SETA 7-14, p.8

⁵¹ UN General Assembly, Convention on the Law of the Sea, (adopted 10 December 1982) (UNCLOS), article 121

⁵² UNCLOS Article 121

Moreover, because of the close approximateness of islands to Turkish shores, Turkey claims that those islands are located on the Turkish Continental shelf, and they do not have their continental shelve, but the islands may possess limited territorial seas. According to Turkey, Greek and the Turkish mainlands should be taken into account for the extension of the continental shelf- not the islands.

3.3 Delimitation of the Continental Shelf between the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, and the French Republic (UK vs France) case

In the case of "Delimitation of the Continental Shelf between the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, and the French Republic" (UK vs. France), the closeness of the British Islands in the English Channel was the cause of the conflict between the two states⁵³. For the resolution of the conflict UK and France engaged in negotiations for the delimitation of their continental shelf boundary from 1970 to 1974.⁵⁴ Some agreements were made between the parties, especially on the west of Greenwich; in principle,⁵⁵ they agreed that the boundaries should be based on the principle of equidistance. However, the two states were in fundamental disagreement regarding the allocation of the continental shelf borderline on the west of Greenwich.⁵⁶ Similarly, in Greece and Turkish case, the UK argued that the boundaries for the continental shelf should be drawn equidistantly between the Channel Islands and the French coast, leaving France with

⁵³ Colson D.A, "The United Kingdom–France Continental Shelf Arbitration" (1978) 72 American Journal of International Law 95, p.97

⁵⁴ Delimitation of the Continental Shelf between the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, and the French Republic (UK, France), 30 June 1977 - 14 March 1978, Volume XVIII pp. 3-413, p.4

⁵⁵ T Colson D.A, "The United Kingdom–France Continental Shelf Arbitration" (1978) 72 American Journal of International Law 95, p.97

⁵⁶ T Colson D.A, "The United Kingdom–France Continental Shelf Arbitration" (1978) 72 American Journal of International Law 95, p.97

restricted maritime jurisdiction. Further, with this division UK would gain absolute jurisdiction over the continental shelf of the English Channel in the area.⁵⁷ On the contrary, the French argued that the mainlands of both states should be taken into account and that the British Islands should be granted no more than 6 miles of jurisdictional range.⁵⁸ Thus, considering that France would almost be landlocked, the arbitral tribunal took into account the French and British mainlands as the criteria for the maritime jurisdictions of both states. Indeed, the case was interpreted as a "special circumstance".⁵⁹ International law does not consider ICJ or tribunal cases as a source for present or future disputes, which is a case for some domestic jurisdictions. Thus, the UK vs. France case cannot be taken into account as a resolution source for Turkey and Greece conflict, but it is worth seeking such a resolution in the Eastern Mediterranean or Aegean sea as well.

3.4 The Continental Shelf (Libyan Arab Jamahiriya/Malta) or (Libya vs. Malta)

The Continental Shelf (Libyan Arab Jamahiriya/Malta)⁶⁰ or (Libya vs. Malta) 1985 is a famous case regarding the island conflicts that have emerged in International Law, which may also be related to the Turkish and Greek conflictual situation. Indeed, Malta is a small Island, and Libya possesses a long mainland coast.⁶¹ During the tribunal, parties requested a judgment from ICJ that would be binding rather than a delimitation, which would also become an initial point for the

⁵⁷ T Colson D.A, "The United Kingdom–France Continental Shelf Arbitration" (1978) 72 American Journal of International Law 95, p.97

⁵⁸ T Colson D.A, "The United Kingdom–France Continental Shelf Arbitration" (1978) 72 American Journal of International Law 95, p.97

⁵⁹ Basaran H.R, "THE LEGAL ASPECTS OF THE EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN QUESTION" [2021] SETA 7-14, p.10

⁶⁰ Continental Shelf (Libyan Arab Jamahiriya/Malta) 1985

⁶¹ Wlosowicz Z, "The Malta/Libya Case: Shelf Delimitation by the Distance Principle and How to Influence Decisions without Intervening" (1985) 44 The Cambridge Law Journal 341-345, p.341

negotiations towards a compromise.⁶² The Court reconsidered the extent of its jurisdiction because of the request made by the parties.⁶³ ICJ indicated that since it was required to determine how the principle and rules of international law could be enforced so that the states may delimit the continental shelf without difficulty, hence, Court decided to reserve an actual delimitation line.⁶⁴

For the applicable law, it was agreed by the Court and from the parties' standpoint that the 1982 UNCLOS had significant importance and found it possible to view the principle of the Convention on delimitation as Customary International Law.⁶⁵ The ICJ enforced Article 83.1 of UNCLOS, which states that to achieve an equitable solution, delimitation of the continental shelf must be effected by agreement on the essence of international law.⁶⁶ However, it was indicated that the Convention set a goal to be achieved but lacked the pass to follow to accomplish it. Furthermore, UNCLOS did not indicate the correlation between the essence of title to the shelf and principles of delimitation, and in this manner, the states were completely at variance.

The Court decided to take into account a much broader context because of the importance given to equitable principles. It was indicated that the coastal relationship in the whole geographical context should be taken into account in a semi-enclosed sea such as the Mediterranean.⁶⁷ Indeed, Libya's argument that the land mass should be taken into account and should become a legal base

⁶² Wlosowicz Z, "The Malta/Libya Case: Shelf Delimitation by the Distance Principle and How to Influence Decisions without Intervening" (1985) 44 The Cambridge Law Journal 341-345, p.341

⁶³ Wlosowicz Z, "The Malta/Libya Case: Shelf Delimitation by the Distance Principle and How to Influence Decisions without Intervening" (1985) 44 The Cambridge Law Journal 341-345, p.342

⁶⁴ Wlosowicz Z, "The Malta/Libya Case: Shelf Delimitation by the Distance Principle and How to Influence Decisions without Intervening" (1985) 44 The Cambridge Law Journal 341-345, p.342

⁶⁵ Wlosowicz Z, "The Malta/Libya Case: Shelf Delimitation by the Distance Principle and How to Influence Decisions without Intervening" (1985) 44 The Cambridge Law Journal 341-345, p.342

⁶⁶ Wlosowicz Z, "The Malta/Libya Case: Shelf Delimitation by the Distance Principle and How to Influence Decisions without Intervening" (1985) 44 The Cambridge Law Journal 341-345, p.341

⁶⁷ Wlosowicz Z, "The Malta/Libya Case: Shelf Delimitation by the Distance Principle and How to Influence Decisions without Intervening" (1985) 44 The Cambridge Law Journal 341-345, p.343

for the state's entitlement to continental shelf rights was rejected by the Court. However, coastal lengths of states were indicated to be relevant in decision-making. Indeed, the Court signified considerable distance between two states and the difference in their coastal lengths; hence, it stressed the significance of proportionality. But no result was reached from the proportionality approach of the Court.

It was argued by Judge Oda of the case that the "equidistance/ special circumstance" has been accepted by the 1958 Geneva Convention on the Continental shelf,⁶⁸ as well as in the 1977 Anglo-French arbitration. Further, this "circumstance" was taken into account in the proceedings, which led to the adoption of the 1982 UNCLOS. However, these details or facts regarding "special circumstances" were given little consideration by the Court during the final decision. The "special circumstance" also appeared in the 1982 Tunisia and Libya Continental shelf dispute and the 1984 Chamber of the Court's Gulf of Maine decision.⁶⁹ Indeed, in Libya vs. Malta case, while making a decision, the Court took into account the uninhabited rocks of Malta and Libya's longer coastline.⁷⁰ Hence, Libya was granted more maritime jurisdiction than Malta. Indeed, considering the geographical circumstance and disadvantages, some adjustments to the borderline were made for an equitable solution.

⁶⁸ Leigh M, "Case Concerning the Continental Shelf (Libyan Arab Jamahiriya/Malta)" (1986) 80 American Journal of International Law 645-648, p.647

⁶⁹ Leigh M, "Case Concerning the Continental Shelf (Libyan Arab Jamahiriya/Malta)" (1986) 80 American Journal of International Law 645-648, p.648

⁷⁰ Leigh M, "Case Concerning the Continental Shelf (Libyan Arab Jamahiriya/Malta)" (1986) 80 American Journal of International Law 645-648, p.645

Chapter 4: Law and Principles

4.1 International Law with a regard to basic Principles

Based on the International Law of the sea, the 1982 UNCLOS, the 1958 Convention on the Continental Shelf, International Customary Law, and multilateral and bilateral international treaties are the major sources for the delimitation of maritime borders.⁷¹ Indeed, the UNCLOS is also considered a Customary International Law, which constitutes a binding effect on all states due to its extensive acceptance by the international community or states. Article 57 of UNCLOS defines the EEZ and gives states the right to extend their sea zones up to 200 nautical miles.⁷² Additionally, article 56 gives coastal states sovereign rights over the sea zones.⁷³ Although coastal states and islands are allowed to claim their Exclusive Economic Zones, the neighboring coastal states' claims may overlap because of the location of some islands that are close to another state, which is also the case in the Turkish-Greek dispute on maritime boundaries. Indeed, the resolution of maritime border disputes are required to be considered on the essence of the applicable international law with regard to the basis such as "equitable solution," "respect to geography," "non-cut-off effect," and "proportionality".⁷⁴

⁷¹ Dixon, Martin. , *Textbook on International Law*, (Fifth edn, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005). p.198

⁷² UN General Assembly, Convention on the Law of the Sea, (adopted 10 December 1982) (UNCLOS), article 57

⁷³ UNCLOS 1982, Article 56

⁷⁴ Erdoğan A, "The Legal and Political Aspects of the Eastern Mediterranean: What Is at Stake?" (2021) 23 *Insight Turkey* pp. 77-98, p.80

4.1.1 The Principle of Equitable Solution principle

Regarding the delimitation of the EEZ, Articles 74(1) and 83(1) of UNCLOS indicate that the delimitation of the Exclusive Economic Zones between states with adjacent coasts should be based on an agreement between the coastal states on the essence of the principle of an equitable solution.⁷⁵ However, a fundamental issue of the delimitation of maritime zones is its high open-endedness, in accordance with the principle of fair or equitable solution and the approach that is used for the delimitation.⁷⁶ Indeed, what might seem like an equitable solution for one party may be an abuse of other states' exclusive rights.

One of the most widely used methods in maritime border disputes for achieving an equitable solution is considering the median line between two coastal states as a borderline. Article 6(1) of the 1958 Convention on the Continental Shelf indicates that the borderline of the continental shelf between two or more states with adjacent coasts to each other is determined by an arrangement or an agreement⁷⁷. Further, if an agreement is not present and unless there is a special circumstance for the justification of the borderline⁷⁸, the article indicated that "the boundary is the median line, every point of which is equidistant from the nearest points of the baselines from which the breadth of the territorial sea of each State is measured."⁷⁹

On the contrary, when the delimitation is determined equidistantly from two coastal states' mainlands, the islands belonging to one state may be located on the wrong side of the borderline

⁷⁵ United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea-Part V Exclusive Economic Zone

⁷⁶ Erdoğan A, "The Legal and Political Aspects of the Eastern Mediterranean: What Is at Stake?" (2021) 23 *Insight Turkey* pp. 77-98, p.81

⁷⁷ International Law Commission, *Convention on the Continental Shelf*, 29 April 1958, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 499, Article 6

⁷⁸ Convention on the Continental Shelf, Article 6

⁷⁹ International Law Commission, *Convention on the Continental Shelf*, 29 April 1958, United Nations, Treaty Series, vol. 499, Article 6

and won't be able to possess their maritime jurisdictions or zones.⁸⁰ In accordance with the delimitation for Exclusive Economic Zones between the two states, the question emerges if the islands should be given absolute effect or restricted effect while delineating delimitation. In that consideration, the cause of the conflict between Turkey and Greece is the status of the Islands in the Eastern Mediterranean, which is also becoming a problem for natural resource discoveries⁸¹. Indeed, Turkish coastlines are surrounded by Greek islands, which are located in close proximity to the Turkish mainland in Eastern Mediterranean. Considering the islands' close proximity, the entitlement of full maritime jurisdiction to them would limit Turkey to a restricted maritime zone, which is not an equitable solution considering that it has the longest continental coast in the Eastern Mediterranean.⁸²

4.1.2 Respecting Geography

During the third UN Conference on the Law of the Seas (UNCLOS III), GASC and Greek delegations declared that islands are no different than continental territories; hence, they are entitled to have maritime zones.⁸³ Further, other than maritime jurisdiction, they shall possess continental shelf, EEZ, contiguous zone, and territorial sea.⁸⁴ Indeed, as section 3.2 of this paper mentions, Greece bases its argument on Article 121(2) of UNCLOS. The article states that “ the territorial sea, the continental shelf, and the exclusive economic zone of an island are determined in conformity with the provisions of this Convention applicable to other land territory.”⁸⁵ Therefore, Greece

⁸⁰ Erdoğan A, “The Legal and Political Aspects of the Eastern Mediterranean: What Is at Stake?” (2021) 23 *Insight Turkey* pp. 77-98, p.81

⁸¹ Erdoğan A, “The Legal and Political Aspects of the Eastern Mediterranean: What Is at Stake?” (2021) 23 *Insight Turkey* pp. 77-98, p.81

⁸² Erdoğan A, “The Legal and Political Aspects of the Eastern Mediterranean: What Is at Stake?” (2021) 23 *Insight Turkey* pp. 77-98, p.81

⁸³ Jacovides A, “Delimitation Practice in the Eastern Mediterranean” (2012) *ERPIC*, pp. 1-6, p.2

⁸⁴ UNCLOS 1982, Article 121

⁸⁵ UNCLOS 1982, Article 121

argued that the Greek Islands and Turkish mainland should be taken into account in the median line of delimitation so that islands would have maritime jurisdiction of their own.

On the other hand, Turkey asserts that geographical determinants such as the location, size, contiguity to the mainland, as well as the continental shelf of another state, and population factors should be taken into account when granting islands maritime jurisdiction or zones.⁸⁶ According to the Republic of Turkey mainlands of two states should be taken as the main grounds for the delimitation of maritime zones. As Turkish Foreign Ministry Spokesman, Hamdi Aksoy, stated, the islands that are located on the opposite side of the borderline cannot create maritime jurisdiction of their own; the mainland of the other coastal states should also be taken into account.⁸⁷

The unique geographical structure of the Eastern Mediterranean is also the main factor that complicates the Greek-Turkish delimitation. Eastern Mediterranean consists of very big islands with a large number of inhabitants, such as Crete and Rhodes, as well as Islands that are tiny and unpopulated or with very little population that may not influence maritime entitlements, such as Kastellorizo.⁸⁸

4.1.3 The Non-Cut off effect and Proportionality principles

Apparently, the Turkish and Greek conflict cannot be resolved on the basis of principles in UNCLOS without taking into consideration the geography of the Eastern Mediterranean. In this particular case, existing legal documents cannot contribute a clear answer regarding the delimitation

⁸⁶ Erdoğan A, "The Legal and Political Aspects of the Eastern Mediterranean: What Is at Stake?" (2021) 23 *Insight Turkey* pp. 77-98, p.82

⁸⁷ Zontur E.C, "Map Delineates Turkey's Maritime Frontiers in E.Med" (*Anadolu Agency*, December 2, 2018) <<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/infographics/map-delineates-turkeys-maritime-frontiers-in-emed/1661791>>

⁸⁸ Yiallourides C, "Part II: Some Observations on the Agreement between Greece and Egypt on the Delimitation of the Exclusive Economic Zone" (*EJIL*, August 23, 2020) <<https://www.ejiltalk.org/part-ii-some-observations-on-the-agreement-between-greece-and-egypt-on-the-delimitation-of-the-exclusive-economic-zone/>>

of islands; thus, one of the widespread practices is to look at the case law, which may provide precedents for such conflicts with appropriate previous court rulings. As mentioned in section 3.3 Channel Islands Case in 1977 is one of the cases that may be taken into consideration; as well as section 3.4, the Libya-Malta Continental Shelf Case of 1985 contributes a significant precedent for the Turkish-Greek conflict over maritime jurisdiction. Considering the semi-enclosed structure of the Mediterranean Sea, which constitutes special circumstances, and Libya's coastal length, the ICJ granted Malta one-fourth of the concerned area and rejected the equidistant or median line between the two states. Indeed, as indicated previously in section 3.4, the coastal length of the states was taken into account as well, despite Malta being an independent island state.

Considering both Malta vs. Libya and UK vs. France cases where the special circumstance is taken into account by the ICJ, Greece's claims that the island of Meis is entitled to the EEZ and continental shelf is baseless.⁸⁹ Indeed, with respect to the principles of proportionality and non-cut-off effect, an equitable agreement may be attained through no maritime jurisdiction originated by the island, or it will be delimited due to the 2 km proximity of the island to the Turkish coastline.⁹⁰ Indeed, Turkey has persistently argued against Greek efforts to declare its Continental shelf and Exclusive Economic Zone for the tiny islands in the proximity of Turkish coasts.

4.2 Libya-Turkey and Egypt-Greece Agreement

In 2019, the Republic of Turkey and Libya's UN-recognized Government of National Accord (GNA) concluded an agreement determining the boundaries of the Continental Shelf and

⁸⁹ Bir B. and Aydın H.K, "Greece Violates Int'l Agreements by Arming 18 Islands" (*Anadolu Agency*, September 13, 2020) <<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/politics/greece-violates-intl-agreements-by-arming-18-islands/1972161>>

⁹⁰ Bir B. and Aydın H.K, "Greece Violates Int'l Agreements by Arming 18 Islands" (*Anadolu Agency*, September 13, 2020) <<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/politics/greece-violates-intl-agreements-by-arming-18-islands/1972161>>

the Libyan and Turkish Exclusive Economic Zones.⁹¹ Both from legal and political perspectives, the agreement between the two states has strengthened Turkey's position in the Eastern Mediterranean. By this act, Turkey prevented a possible agreement that Libya GNA may have concluded with GASC, Greece, Egypt, and Israel against Turkey's interests.⁹² Indeed, Article 4 of the agreement or memorandum constitutes significance in its context for future delimitation agreements and possible disputes that may arise surrounding maritime zones in the Mediterranean.⁹³ Further, Article 4(2) in the Turkish-Libyan maritime delimitation agreement indicates that states may cooperate for joint exploitation of the potential natural resources found in the EEZ of one party and ranging to the other state's EEZ. Additionally, based on Article 4(3) of the agreement, in case either one of the states is involved in negotiations regarding the delimitation of its EEZ, the party shall notify and negotiate with the other party prior to concluding an agreement.⁹⁴

On the other hand, both states have been put into adverse circumstances with other coastal states. The agreement was considered to be undermining the regional status quo, and it was declared to be "null and void" by Greece and Egypt, as well as France and Cyprus.⁹⁵ Additionally, as a

⁹¹ "Memorandum of Understanding Between The Government of The Republic of Turkey and The Government of National Accord-State of Libya on Delimitation of the Maritime Jurisdiction Areas in the Mediterranean," *T.C Resmi Gazete*(December 7, 2019) (Official Gazete of Turkish Republic)

⁹² Yüzbaşıoğlu N, "Dışişleri Bakanlığı Sözcüsü Aksoy: Türkiye Ve Libya Oldubittilere İzin Vermeyecek" (*Anadolu Agency*, December 1, 2019) <<https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/turkiye/disisleri-bakanligi-sozcusu-aksoy-turkiye-ve-libya-oldubittilere-izin-vermeyecek/1660813>>

⁹³ "Memorandum of Understanding Between The Government of The Republic of Turkey and The Government of National Accord-State of Libya on Delimitation of the Maritime Jurisdiction Areas in the Mediterranean," *T.C Resmi Gazete*(December 7, 2019) (Official Gazete of Turkish Republic)

⁹⁴ "Memorandum of Understanding Between The Government of The Republic of Turkey and The Government of National Accord-State of Libya on Delimitation of the Maritime Jurisdiction Areas in the Mediterranean," *T.C Resmi Gazete*(December 7, 2019) (Official Gazete of Turkish Republic)

⁹⁵ Al Jazeera, "Four Mediterranean Countries Call Turkey-GNA Deals 'Void'" (*Fossil Fuels News | Al Jazeera*, January 9, 2020) <<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/1/9/four-mediterranean-countries-call-turkey-gna-deals-void>>

response to the Turkish-Libyan agreement, Greece and Egypt signed a treaty on the delimitation of maritime jurisdiction. The treaty apparently aims to restrict Turkey's maritime territorial claims. In return, the Turkish Foreign Ministry declared the deal "null and void" and indicated that Egypt and Greece do not share maritime boundaries.⁹⁶ Further, Ankara stated that the demarcated areas in the agreement were located on Turkey's continental shelf, and the issue has been reported to the UN.⁹⁷ Thus, because of the agreements concluded by both Turkey and Greece, overlapping claims for Exclusive Economic Zones were established in Eastern Mediterranean.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

In conclusion, the shortcomings of Maritime Law have become obvious in the Eastern Mediterranean conflict. Despite having a comprehensive Convention such as UNCLOS, geographical circumstance has overcome the solutions which are offered in the textually based Laws.

The problem starts with the UNCLOS granting Islands the to possess their own maritime jurisdiction. Indeed, by this act, the drafters of the Convention already had disregarded the neighboring States with Sovereign Island states such as Malta. Further, the states with Islands, such as Greece or UK. The conflicts have emerged because of the close proximity of the islands or because they are located in the EEZ of the other state.

The Eastern Mediterranean is one of the special circumstances which should be taken into account without the consideration of textual-based laws. Indeed, special cases such as Malta vs. Libya and UK vs. France should be taken into account while the decision-making process. It is also

⁹⁶ "Turkey Declares Egypt-Greece Maritime Deal 'Null and Void'" (*Middle East Eye* August 6, 2020) <<https://www.middleeasteye.net/news/turkey-slams-egypt-greece-maritime-agreement-eastern-mediterranean>> accessed August 25, 2022

⁹⁷ Durul T, "Greece Ratifies Maritime Deal Signed with Egypt" (*Anadolu Agency*, August 27, 2020) <<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/europe/greece-ratifies-maritime-deal-signed-with-egypt/1955533#>>

worth noting that the conflictual state has not applied to the ICJ regarding the dispute. The conflict has been going back and forth on an interstate level.

Indeed, the finding shows that the close proximity of the Greece Islands would landlock Turkey. In this instance, good faith and the violation of Turkey's EEZ will occur. Taking into consideration that the decisions shall be made in good faith, the Eastern Mediterranean conflict shall be treated as a special circumstance, and, if necessary previous cases shall be taken into account as precedents for the particular dispute. Therefore, it is recommended that the mainlands of the two states should be taken as a base for their Maritime jurisdictions. Lastly, to have an equitable solution and for the equal distribution of the Maritime zones.

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